

A Study on Impact of Socio – Economic Characteristics on Brand Sticking Tendency with Special Reference to Fastrack Hand Bags

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Abstract

Purses and handbags have their origins in early pouches used to carry seeds, religious items and medicine. Early on, both men and women carried pouches. Years ago, it was ladylike to carry as little as possible. A small bag was typical. Today women are gone from home for longer periods of time, frequently working or if not, often with children along. The size of the typical bag has increased to meet the need. Need satisfaction is very important in marketing. Customers buy goods for the satisfaction of their wants. Once the customer satisfied with their products they cannot change their views. As satisfaction of customers plays a major role in marketing it has assumed growing importance under customer-oriented marketing planning and management. Conducting study on brand sticking tendency is the attempt to understand and predict human action in the buying role.

Keywords: Brand sticking, Hand bag, impact, Socio – economic characteristics, Tendency

Introduction

Bags and purses were used by both men and women to store and carry money and other pertinent personal items. Early on, they carried them on a leather strap around their waist. Pockets appeared in men's clothing around the late 16th century and early 17th century and the bag fell into disuse among men with the exception of game bags and briefcases. Bags became the exclusive domain of women in succeeding centuries. As fashion evolved throughout the centuries, so did the handbag. Handbags have become empowering items in our society. They are powerful implements that we carry dearly, daily and out of necessity. They are fascinating pieces of history that offer a reflective view of our past, present and future.¹ Today handbags are not just a fashion statement and they are not just for practical purpose, the need to be both. The recent trend is away from backpacks style and toward and oversized handbags. Women want a more fashionable handbag that can also be used as a briefcase, laptop case and handbag, and even baby bag. Handbags go back to the beginning of time and have become a practicality and a fashion statement for women of all ages.²

Statement of the problem

Nowadays, there are many brands of hand bags available in Krishnagiri district. Recently, Fastrack hand bag is the popular brand and it provides quality hand bags at affordable prices to the customer. Though there exist many positive thoughts in customer perception, some Fastrack hand bag users are not having brand sticking tendency. They tend to switch over to other brands shortly. To find solution to this problem the study on the impact of socio – economic characteristics on brand

sticking tendency with special reference to Fastrack hand bags has been undertaken.

Objectives of the study

The objective of this study is to find the impact of socio – economic characteristics on the brand sticking tendency of Fastrack hand bag users in Fastrack hand bag.

Methodology and tools

This study is an empirical research. The primary data were collected in krisnagiry district during the year 2015 by using interview schedule. Survey method is adopted for this study. Data were collected directly from the sample respondents by interviewing them personally.

Sampling design

The sample respondents should be the representatives of the population. In such a way the sample respondents are selected by using non-probability convenience sampling method. The Krishnagiri district was selected for this study. By considering the time, the sample size of 50 respondents was selected by using the above sampling design.

Area of the study

The area of the study is confined to Krishnagiri district.

Findings

Socio-economic characteristics may influence the brand sticking tendency of Fastrack hand bag users. In order to find the relationship between socio-economic characteristics and the brand sticking tendency of Fastrack hand bag users, the following statistical analysis has been made on the basis of following null hypothesis.

H₀: There is no relationship between socio-economic characteristics and the brand sticking tendency of Fastrack hand bag users.

¹ <http://business.mapsofindia.com/top-brands-india/handbag.html>

² <http://thesack.org/history.php>

This null hypothesis has been statistically tested with the help of chi-square test at 5% level of significance.

Age and the brand sticking tendency of Fastrack hand bag users

Some features of a product may attract a particular age group people and the same may not attract other age group people. Old age people may know the real world by having more experience. Hence the brand sticking tendency of Fastrack hand bag users differ according to their age. By having this in mind, the relationship between age and brand sticking tendency of Fastrack hand bag users has been studied. Table 1 shows the relationship between age and the brand sticking tendency of Fastrack hand bag users.

Table 1: Age and the brand sticking tendency of Fastrack hand bag users: χ^2 test

S. No	Age Group	No. of respondents		
		Sticking Tendency	Switching Tendency	Total
1	Less than 18 years	06	02	08
2	19 – 35 years	16	04	20
3	36 – 60 years	13	03	16
4	Above 60 years	05	01	06
	Total	40	10	50

$\chi^2 = 0.182$ Degree of freedom = 3 Table Value = 7.81

The calculated value of χ^2 is less than the table value. The relationship between age and the brand sticking tendency of Fastrack hand bag users is insignificance. Hence it can be concluded that the framed null hypothesis is accepted and there is no relationship between age and brand sticking tendency of Fastrack hand bag users.

Gender and the brand sticking tendency of Fastrack hand bag users

Male and female are having different nature and character. So the brand sticking tendency of Fastrack hand bag users may vary according to their gender. In this background, the relationship between gender and the brand sticking tendency

of Fastrack hand bag users has been studied. Table 2 and Chart 2 show that the relationship between gender and brand sticking tendency of Fastrack hand bag users.

Table 2: Gender and the brand sticking tendency of Fastrack hand bag users: χ^2 test

S. No	Gender	No. of respondents		
		Sticking Tendency	Switching Tendency	Total
1	Male	18	03	21
2	Female	22	07	29
	Total	40	10	50

$\chi^2 = 0.739$ Degree of freedom = 1 Table Value = 3.84

The calculated value of χ^2 is less than the table value. The relationship between gender and the brand sticking tendency of Fastrack hand bag users is insignificance. Hence it can be concluded that the framed null hypothesis is accepted and there is no relationship between gender and the brand sticking tendency of Fastrack hand bag users.

Marital status and the brand sticking tendency of Fastrack hand bag users

Married people are having more responsibility than unmarried people. So the purchase decision and awareness about the product may differ according to their marital status. In this regard, the relationship between marital status and the brand sticking tendency of Fastrack hand bag users has been studied. Table 3 shows that the relationship between marital status and the brand sticking tendency of Fastrack hand bag users.

Table 3: Marital status and the brand sticking tendency of Fastrack hand bag users: χ^2 test

S. No	Marital Status	No. of respondents		
		Sticking Tendency	Switching Tendency	Total
1	Married	25	06	31
2	Unmarried	15	04	19
	Total	40	10	50

$\chi^2 = 0.022$ Degree of freedom = 1 Table Value = 3.84

The calculated value of χ^2 is less than the table value. The relationship between marital status and the brand sticking tendency of Fastrack hand bag users is insignificant. Hence it can be concluded that the framed null hypothesis is accepted and there is no relationship between marital status and the brand sticking tendency of Fastrack hand bag users.

Educational status and the brand sticking tendency of Fastrack hand bag users

Normally the educated people have more ability to perceive anything easily when compared to illiterate. The most of the illiterate people don't have ability to understand quickly. Mostly the educated people have better knowledge than the illiterate. In this regard, an attempt has been made to study the relationship between educational status and the brand sticking tendency of Fastrack hand bag users has been studied. Table 4 and Chart 4 show that the relationship between educational status and brand sticking tendency of Fastrack hand bag users.

Table 4: Educational status and the brand sticking tendency of Fastrack hand bag users: χ^2 test

S.No	Educational Status	No. of respondents		
		Sticking Tendency	Switching Tendency	Total
1	Illiterate	09	02	11
2	School level	17	04	21
3	College level	14	04	18
	Total	40	10	50

$\chi^2 = 0.0896$ Degree of freedom = 2 Table Value = 5.99

The calculated value of χ^2 is less than the table value. The relationship between educational status and the brand sticking tendency of Fastrack hand bag users is insignificant. Hence it can be concluded that the framed null hypothesis is accepted and there is no relationship between educational status and the brand sticking tendency of Fastrack hand bag users.

Occupation and the brand sticking tendency of Fastrack hand bag users

The people may have different experience and different relationship with other people in this world according to their occupation. So the brand sticking tendency of Fastrack hand bag users may affect a different people according to their occupation. In this regard, to analyse the relationship between occupation and the brand sticking tendency of Fastrack hand bag users has been studied. Table 5 and Chart 5 show that the relationship between occupation and the brand sticking tendency of Fastrack hand bag users.

Table 5: Distribution of sample respondents according to their occupation and the brand sticking tendency of Fastrack hand bag users: χ^2 test

S. No	Occupation	No. of respondents		
		Sticking Tendency	Switching Tendency	Total
1	Employee	05	03	08
2	Business	07	01	08
3	Agriculture	09	01	10
4	Student	06	02	08
5	Others	13	03	16
	Total	40	10	50

$\chi^2 = 2.579$ Degree of freedom = 4 Table Value = 9.49

The calculated value of χ^2 is less than the table value. The relationship between occupation and the brand sticking tendency of Fastrack hand bag users is insignificant. Hence it can be concluded that the framed null hypothesis is accepted and there is no relationship between occupation and the brand sticking tendency of Fastrack hand bag users.

Income level and the brand sticking tendency of Fastrack hand bag users

If a person earns huge money, he can buy anything as he like. On the other hand, the person who earns less money, they

don't have surplus money to buy anything as they like. From this, we can study the relationship between income level and the brand sticking tendency of Fastrack hand bag users has been studied. Table 6 and Chart 6 show that the relationship between income level and the brand sticking tendency of Fastrack hand bag users.

Table 6: Distribution of sample respondents according to their income level and the brand sticking tendency of Fastrack hand bag users: χ^2 test

S. No	Income Level	No. of respondents		
		Sticking Tendency	Switching Tendency	Total
1	Below Rs. 10000	21	03	24
2	Rs. 10000 – Rs. 25000	09	06	15
3	Above Rs. 25000	10	01	11
	Total	40	10	50

$\chi^2 = 5.413$ Degree of freedom = 2 Table Value = 5.99

The calculated value of χ^2 is less than the table value. The relationship between income level and the brand sticking tendency of Fastrack hand bag users is insignificant. Hence it can be concluded that the framed null hypothesis is accepted and there is no relationship between income level and the brand sticking tendency of Fastrack hand bag users.

Type of family and the brand sticking tendency of Fastrack hand bag users

Mostly the joint family consists of both old and young persons. The old people are well experienced than the young people. Both old and young people may share their experience to other persons in the family. So the sticking tendency may affect the people according to the type of family. In this background, to analyse the relationship between type of family and the brand sticking tendency of Fastrack hand bag users has been studied. Table 7 and Chart 7 show that the relationship between type of family and the brand sticking tendency of Fastrack hand bag users.

Table 7: Distribution of sample respondents according to their type of family and the brand sticking tendency of Fastrack hand bag users: χ^2 test

S. No	Type of family	No. of respondents		
		Sticking Tendency	Switching Tendency	Total
1	Nuclear family	21	07	28
2	Joint family	19	03	22
	Total	40	10	50

$\chi^2 = 0.9944$ Degree of freedom = 1 Table Value = 3.84

The calculated value of χ^2 is less than the table value. The relationship between type of family and the brand sticking tendency of Fastrack hand bag users is insignificant. Hence it can be concluded that the framed null hypothesis is accepted and there is no relationship between type of family and the brand sticking tendency of Fastrack hand bag users.

Summary

From this study it is found that out of 50 sample respondents, 40 respondents are having sticking tendency in Fastrack hand bag. The remaining 10 respondents are having switching tendency in Fastrack hand bag.

The entire socio-economic characteristics (age, gender, marital status, educational status, occupation, income level, type of family and size of family) of the respondents has been tested with the effect of satisfaction level of sticking tendency by using chi-square test at 5% level of significance.

This study also shows that there is no relationship between the socio-economic characteristics of sample respondents and the brand sticking tendency of Fastrack hand bag users. The brand sticking tendency of Fastrack hand bag users are not affected by socio-economic characteristics.

Suggestion and recommendations

On the basis of the findings of the study, it is suggested to implement the following suggestion and recommendations to improve the Fastrack hand bag in the entire manner.

1. The company may provide after sale service to retain their customers.
2. Introduction of cash back offer would attract new customers.
3. Providing warranty for hand bag will create good image about Fastrack hand bag in the minds of public.
4. Introducing the new designs will attract the youngsters.

These are all the suggestions and recommendations provided by the customers to improve the Fastrack hand bag.

Conclusion

Customer perception plays a major role in marketing. This study reveals the customer perception towards Fastrack hand bag. It can be known from this study the majority of the sample respondents are highly satisfied with Fastrack hand bag and having the brand sticking tendency. Once the customers are fixed with the product they cannot get back to the other one. Most of the respondents are highly aware about the Fastrack hand bag. Only a few number of respondents are feel that the Fastrack hand bag has giving some problems. If this company satisfy those people it can be firmly say that the Fastrack hand bag will be the popular brand of all other brands.

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